

SOUTHERN CYBERSPACE

The information revolution promises to accelerate advances in science. But some observers fear it will leave researchers in the developing world even farther behind.

HISTORY SHOWS THAT ADVANCES IN TECHNOLOGY OFTEN ENHANCE EXISTING INEQUALITIES. A RECENT STUDY BY THE U.S. NATIONAL TELECOMMUNICATIONS AND INFORMATION ADMINISTRATION, FOR EXAMPLE, REVEALED THAT WHILE ACCESS TO COMPUTERS, MODEMS AND ONLINE CONNECTIVITY INCREASED

throughout the United States between 1994 and 1997, the gap between the rich (mainly white and non-Hispanic immigrants) and the disadvantaged (mainly black, Hispanic and inner city populations) had widened considerably.

Let us consider scientific research in India. Researchers must find out what is happening around the world as well as keep others informed about what they are doing. Information is the key to knowledge and dissemination of information crucial for the scientific enterprise.

In pre-independent India, when such world-class scientists as C.V. Raman, Meghnad Saha and J.C. Bose made their critical contributions to knowledge, professional journals served as the main vehicle for scholarly communication. Scientists worldwide had virtually the same level of access to information, although those working in developing countries received their journals a few months later than their European colleagues.

Despite the tremendous proliferation of journals today, many of them remain beyond the reach of libraries and research institutes in the South, especially journals published by commercial firms. The best academic science library in India, at the Indian Institute of Science, receives some 1,560 serials, including those that arrive free of charge or through an exchange. In the United States and Europe, many university libraries subscribe to some 50,000 journal titles.

To make matters worse, due to the rising value of the U.S. dollar on international currency markets and dramatic increases in subscription prices, libraries in India and other developing nations have been forced to reduce the number of journals and data bases they receive. The situation in Africa is particularly bad. "When you call some of us scientists," an African professor recently told a journalist, "we laugh at ourselves. We know we can no longer make contributions to science. I do not know what my colleagues in Kenya or London have found, for example. So I cannot carry out an experiment and believe I am on the path to an original contribution....If I have been giving generations of students the same notes for the last 10 years, I should not call myself a scientist."

Now, many primary journals and data base collections have gone electronic. Title-listing services such as *Current Contents Connect*, abstracting services such as *SciFinder* and multidisciplinary citation indexes such as *Web of Science* are available on the web—at a fee that most university and research laboratory libraries in developing

countries cannot afford. Many frontline journals have become increasingly accessible via password controls on the web through, for example, Elsevier's *Science Direct*.

Physicists have gone a step further. They circulate preprints electronically, via Los Alamos National Laboratory's *e-Print* archive, long before a hardcopy is printed in refereed journals. This service is offered free of charge to physicists worldwide. In theory, anyone anywhere in the world can use this service. In reality, though, one must have access to the appropriate technology, which most scientists in developing countries do not have. As a result, the performance of researchers can be adversely affected not because of their work but because they are not connected to electronic information networks.

Accessing information through CD-ROMs offers capabilities not possible through print, and accessing through the web offers capabilities not possible through CD-ROMs. As a recent editorial in *Science* noted, "Digital publishing has much to recommend it over print publishing...Uncomfortable trade-offs are involved...but the gains include ease of access, rapid delivery over great distances, and hypertext links from indexing services and bibliographic citations to the full text of cited documents."

Hardly any laboratory in the developing world has web access to these databases. How can scientists working in these laboratories be equal partners in the worldwide enterprise of knowledge production? The truth is that the transition from hard copies to electronic publishing likely will widen the gap between developed countries and developing countries and further marginalize already marginalized scientists and scholars in the South.

Most developing countries do not have the necessary infrastructure (computer terminals, networks, communication channels and bandwidths) to become equal partners in worldwide knowledge production and dissemination. According to Bruce Girard, former director of Latin America's community radio Pulsar, 95 percent of all computers are located in developed nations, and 10 developed nations, accounting for 20 percent of the world's population, have 75 percent of the world's telephone lines. Teledensity in India today is slightly less than 2 lines per 100 persons. This marks a vast improvement. Less than five years ago, teledensity in India was 1 line per 100 persons. In contrast, however, teledensity in the United States and Canada is more than 60 per 100 inhabitants. To make matters worse, most of India's telephones are concentrated in the largest metropolitan areas.

Many Indian universities, moreover, do not have e-mail or internet facilities. And those that do have such low bandwidths and poor terrestrial telephone connections that researchers remain

unable to surf the net or do online searches. Dated technology restricts them to sending and receiving e-mail messages.

Those connected to new information technologies undoubtedly are much better off than before. But a vast majority of scientists in developing countries do not have access.

Take, for instance, the *e-Print* archive. This information service is available to physicists at only a few institutes in India—for example, the Indian Institute of Science, Institute of Mathematical Sciences and Tata Institute of Fundamental Research. More disturbingly, Indian physicists in such leading universities as the University of Delhi, Banaras Hindu University and University of Madras are not connected to the internet or e-mail at all. In contrast, every physicist in the United States and the United Kingdom enjoys easy access to e-mail and the internet.

The disadvantages that this disparity poses for scientists in developing countries are obvious. A growing number of journals, especially in the fields of science and technology, now receive and review manuscripts via e-mail and some journals are available only in electronic form. Editors of such journals likely will be reluctant to use referees from developing countries, even if they are exceptionally competent in their fields because it would be difficult to reach them electronically. Besides, many scientists in developing countries will be unable to publish their work in electronic journals.

The United Nations has voiced its concerns about the imbalance in access to electronic communication facilities. The UN's Administrative Committee on Coordination, issued a statement on Universal Access to Basic Communication and Information Services in April 1997 in which it stated: "We are profoundly concerned at the deepening maldistribution of access, resources and opportunities in the information and communication field. The information technology gap and related inequities between industrialized and developing nations are widening: a new type of poverty—information poverty—looms. Most developing countries, especially the least developed countries (LDCs) are not sharing in the communication revolution, since they lack:

- Affordable access to core information resources, cutting-edge technology and sophisticated telecommunication systems and infrastructure.
- The capacity to build, operate, manage, and service the technologies involved.
- Policies that promote equitable public participation in the information society as both producers and consumers of information and knowledge.
- A workforce trained to develop, maintain and provide the value-added products and services required by the information economy."

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The communication revolution is perceived as a liberating force. Yet, what is most likely to happen is that scientists and scholars in many developing countries will be among the last to join the revolution. In India, for example, the stock market community has a network of its own with dedicated telephone lines, but a vast majority of scientists do not even have telephones on their desks. The low level of information and communication technologies in developing countries may exclude a majority of scientists and scholars in these countries from the collective international discourse that is so essential for active participation in all fields of research.

Even today, when much publishing takes place in print, participation by developing country scientists in such high impact journals as *Science*, *Nature* and *Cell*, remains abysmally low. The gap in science and technology that now exists between developed and developing countries will widen. That, in turn, could exacerbate the "brain drain" problem and intensify the reliance that developing nations have for knowledge developed beyond their borders.

In an earlier era, Indian mathematician, Srinivasa Ramanujan, a genius who had not gone through a conventional training programme, was nurtured in the intellectually stimulating ambience of

Cambridge University thanks to the foresight of G.H. Hardy. While such individual efforts may still help overcome obstacles on occasion, we need a more organized and systematic programme of action to combat the current crisis. Educational institutions and research laboratories must be granted satellite-based high-bandwidth access to the internet at low cost. At the same time, differential price strategies must be devised to allow institutions throughout the developing world to obtain the most recent journal titles and most up-to-date data bases.

On both fronts, I am not optimistic. For example, a proposal by V.S. Arunachalam of Carnegie-Mellon University in the United States to network 100 or so of India's academic and research cities has yet to see the light of day. A report submitted to the then Prime Minister, I. K. Gujral, by the Scientific Advisory Committee to the Indian Cabinet about a year ago has not been acted upon. Fortunately, the recommendations of the taskforce set up by Prime Minister A.B. Vajpayee, of which M.G.K. Menon, a Fellow of TWAS, is a key member and vice chairman, have been accepted by the government and will soon be implemented.

The dithering and slow pace of progress are all too characteristic of the Third World. It often takes far too much time to translate something from the realm of the possible to reality. Part of the blame, I think, rests with the academic community itself. No one ever complains. When things are not working out well, one must learn to complain, protest and demand appropriate action.

As for differential pricing, both publishers of primary journals and database producers are reluctant to embrace such measures. In a rare exception, the Institute for Scientific Information, in Philadelphia, Pennsylvania (USA), offers most developing country subscribers its Science Citation Index at 50-percent discount. Even then it is perceived as too costly.

Given all these circumstances, I would not be surprised if the gap between the scientifically advanced nations and the others widens even further, limiting the role of developing countries in the production, dissemination and utilization of knowledge even more than it is today. ■

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